

Modeling Interphalangeal Joints for Swelling Assessment in Psoriatic Arthritis via Smartphone Photographs

Georgios Apostolidis¹, Eleni Vasileiou¹, Ioanna Katsigianni², Maria Mytilinaiou²,
Theodoros Dimitroulas², Batoul Hojeij³, Jolanda Luime³, Ilja Tchetverikov^{4,5},
Laura Coates⁶, Vasileios Charisis¹, and Leontios Hadjileontiadis^{1,7}

Abstract—Digital assessment of swollen joints from smartphone photographs can support remote monitoring of patients with inflammatory arthritis, enabling more efficient care delivery. In this study, we propose a method to classify each interphalangeal joint in hand photographs as swollen or not. The classifier is a logistic regression model that uses joint effective width as the main predictor, with covariates including age, sex, body mass index, and the joint type. Effective width measures the thickness of a joint and is derived using computer vision algorithms that segment individual fingers, detect joint landmarks, and calculate distances between points of interest. We validated the model using a dataset collected from 85 individuals with psoriatic arthritis recruited between December 2024 and April 2025 across three countries. For each participant, the dataset includes paired photographs of both hands, captured by the participants themselves, along with demographic and clinical data reported by healthcare professionals. Model validation was performed using k-fold cross-validation, ensuring each validation fold contained exactly one patient with at least one swollen joint. The method achieved an average area under the ROC curve (AUROC) of 0.68 (SD 0.29). These findings demonstrate the potential of smartphone-based joint modeling as a scalable and patient-friendly approach to enhance remote assessment and personalized management of psoriatic arthritis.

Index Terms—swollen joint assessment, interphalangeal joint modeling, smartphone digital biomarker, psoriatic arthritis

I. INTRODUCTION

Psoriatic arthritis (PsA) is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting both the peripheral and axial skeleton. It has an

iPROLEPSIS has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095697

¹G. Apostolidis, E. Vasileiou, V. Charisis, and L. Hadjileontiadis are with the Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece. Corresponding author: G. Apostolidis (gapostol@auth.gr)

²I. Katsigianni, M. Mytilinaiou, Th. Dimitroulas are with the Fourth Department of Internal Medicine, Hippokraton Hospital, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

³B. Hojeij and J. Luime is with the Department of Public Health, Erasmus MC, University Medical Center Rotterdam, the Netherlands

⁴I. Tchetverikov is with the Department of Rheumatology, Albert Schweitzer Hospital, Dordrecht, the Netherlands

⁵I. Tchetverikov is also with the Stichting Cicero-Collectief Initiatief Voor Creatief En Educatief Reuma Onderzoek, the Netherlands

⁶L. Coates is with the Nuffield Department of Orthopaedics, Rheumatology and Musculoskeletal Sciences, University of Oxford, Oxford, United Kingdom

⁷L. Hadjileontiadis is also as an Adjunct Professor with the Department of Biomedical Engineering & Biotechnology, Khalifa University, Abu Dhabi, UAE.

estimated prevalence of 1–2% in the general population and significantly reduces patients’ quality of life [1]. PsA is strongly associated with psoriasis (PsO), with up to 30% of individuals living with PsO expected to develop PsA during their lifetime [2]. Hand function impairment is common and significant among patients with PsA [3]. Joint inflammation causes pain, tenderness, and swelling, which may be localized to a single joint or extend across an entire digit. Symptoms can also involve the foot joints, spine, and skin. Early diagnosis and effective monitoring of PsA are critical, as they improve quality of life and help prevent permanent joint damage [4].

In clinical practice, the assessment of PsA includes evaluation of joints using swollen and tender joint counts. Joint examination involves applying pressure (approximately 4 kg/cm²) to assess tenderness and swelling, scored as swollen or not swollen [5]. The scores are summed to determine the total number of swollen joints. Common joint counts used for PsA assessment include the 28-joint count, the 76/78-swollen joint counts (SJC76), and the 66/68-swollen joint counts (SJC66) [5]. However, these assessments are subjective, relying on palpation and clinical judgment, and require experienced rheumatologists.

Advances in digital health technologies have the potential to address challenges in rheumatology through hybrid patient pathways that combine in-person and remote care [6]. Specifically for hand joint swelling assessment, the Psorcast suite of mobile applications has introduced several smartphone-based assessments [7]. One such tool is the “Hand image processing” module, which generates hand landmarks on the palm and finger joints from images and processes them to estimate joint thickness. For generating hand and joint landmarks, the Mediapipe framework [8] was employed. Additionally, Hugel et al. proposed an AI-based approach to detect and monitor joint swelling in patients with rheumatoid arthritis [9]. Their method involves extracting dorsal finger fold lines and processing them using a convolutional neural network (CNN) to classify joints as swollen or not. Similarly, Phatak et al. developed a method for analyzing smartphone photographs of hands to detect inflammation in three selected joints, the index and middle proximal interphalangeal (PIP) joints and the wrist—using a CNN model [10]. Their model, based on the ResNet101 architecture, was trained and evaluated on a dataset of hand photographs from 100 patients. The CNN achieved its best

performance at the middle finger PIP (83/77/88), followed by the index PIP (74/74/75) and the wrist (62/90/21) for accuracy/sensitivity/specificity. However, their method was not assessed for detecting swelling in distal interphalangeal (DIP) joints.

This work aims to digitally characterize interphalangeal joints as swollen or not using logistic regression modeling applied to smartphone photographs. The logistic regression model uses the effective width of the joint, a metric reflecting joint thickness, as its primary predictor, with age, sex, body mass index (BMI), and joint type (i.e. PIP or DIP) included as covariates. The effective width plays a central role in the proposed method. Its calculation involves developing a pipeline of computer vision algorithms that segment individual fingers, detect joint landmarks, and compute distances between points of interest. Finally, we validated the model on data from 85 individuals with PsA, including pairs of hand photographs taken under real-life conditions using the miPROLEPSIS mobile app (<https://www.iprolepsis.eu>) and demographic and clinical information reported by healthcare professionals.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset

A cohort of 85 adults with PsA was recruited between December 2024 and April 2025 across three countries (the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, and Greece) as part of the ‘‘PsA Digital Phenotyping and Inflammation Drivers’’ (PDPID) study, which belongs to the iPROLEPSIS project [11]. The general objective of the PDPID study is to leverage the widespread use of smartphones and smartwatches to enable unobtrusive, remote monitoring of disease activity through device sensor data.

As part of the PDPID study, patients captured photographs of their hands for the digital assessment of swollen joints, either independently or with assistance from healthcare professionals in the clinic. These images were collected using the miPROLEPSIS app, a mobile application developed to support the study. Patients received instructions to ensure high-quality images, including placing the dorsal side of the hand on a surface with high contrast to their skin (ideally white paper) and keeping their fingers separated. Healthcare professionals also recorded clinical assessments, including joint examinations, to provide ground truth data. The cohort was evenly distributed by sex (42 male, 43 female), with a mean age of 52.6 years (SD 11.8) and a mean BMI of 28.94 kg/m² (SD 6.43). Ten participants had at least one swollen interphalangeal joint, with a total of 40 swollen interphalangeal joints reported in the cohort. A panel with example photographs from the dataset is shown in Fig. 1. These examples were selected to highlight the heterogeneity of image views, despite the instructions provided, illustrating the challenges of analyzing smartphone photographs captured in real-life settings.

Fig. 1. A panel of example hand photographs from the dataset.

B. Interphalangeal joint modeling

Swelling of a joint appears as an abnormal increase in size. In interphalangeal joints, one way to measure this enlargement is by comparing the width of the DIP or PIP joint to the distance between them, a metric known as effective width [7]. This measure can be derived from hand photographs using computer vision techniques. However, effective width alone cannot accurately predict interphalangeal joint swelling, as it is influenced by other factors such as anatomical characteristics. Therefore, we propose a model that incorporates effective width along with covariates such as age, BMI, sex, and joint type (PIP or DIP) to improve swelling detection performance.

Calculating the effective width from smartphone photographs involves several steps. First, hand landmarks are detected using the MediaPipe Hand Landmarker [8], which provides coordinates for the hand joints and fingertips. These landmarks are used throughout the effective width calculation process. Next, a neural network, specifically, the U²-Net pretrained for human segmentation [12], is applied to the photograph to generate a hand segmentation mask. After segmentation, the contour of the hand is extracted. By combining the hand contour with the finger landmarks, the contours of individual fingers are extracted. The contour points of each finger allow cropping of the finger into a rectangular bounding box encompassing all contour points. For each finger, the widths of the PIP and DIP joints (W) and the distance between PIP and DIP joints (D) are measured in pixels. The effective width (EFW) of each interphalangeal joint is defined as:

$$\bar{D} = 1/4 \cdot (D_{index} + D_{middle} + D_{ring} + D_{pinkie}), \quad (1)$$

$$EFW_i^k = \frac{W_i^k}{\bar{D}}, \quad (2)$$

where $i \in \{index, middle, ring, pinkie\}$ and $k \in \{PIP, DIP\}$. Here, \bar{D} represents the average PIP-DIP distance and serves as a common denominator for all effective width calculations in the hand. Note that this definition of effective width does not apply to the thumb. The effective width calculation process is illustrated in Fig. 2.

The logistic regression model that classifies a joint as

Fig. 2. The effective width calculation process. A six-step processing workflow from input photograph to effective width calculation: (1) image acquisition, (2) landmark detection, (3) hand segmentation, (4) contour extraction, (5) finger cropping, and (6) width measurement. Bottom panel shows representative outputs at each processing stage.

swollen or not is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{logit}(P(\text{Swollen} = 1)) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot EFW + \\ & \beta_2 \cdot \text{Age} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{BMI} + \\ & \beta_4 \cdot \text{Male} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{DIP}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where EFW , Age , and BMI are numerical variables, while $Male$ and DIP are binary ones. The regression coefficients β_j are estimated by maximizing the penalized log-likelihood with an L2 penalty term $\lambda \|\beta\|^2$.

C. Validation

Model validation employed k-fold cross-validation, with each validation fold containing precisely one patient exhibiting at least one swollen joint. Additionally, a nested cross-validation strategy was used to select the inverse regularization parameter $C = 1/\lambda$. Specifically, a grid search was conducted in the inner loop to identify the value of C that maximized the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC) on the validation set. The range of C values tested is $[0.01, 0.1, 1, 10, 100]$.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The true and false positive rates from the best model in each inner loop were retained for cumulative ROC analysis. Fig. 3 shows the average ROC curve along with upper and lower standard deviation bands. Additionally, the mean and standard deviation of the AUROC metric were calculated to assess overall model performance. The results indicate good performance, although variability across folds is substantial.

The importance of the independent variables was evaluated by examining the logistic regression coefficient magnitudes. Higher absolute coefficient values reflect a greater contribution to classification. Since regularization was applied,

Fig. 3. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve showing the average swollen joint classification performance of the proposed logistic regression model, with shaded bands representing the standard deviation across cross-validation folds.

coefficient magnitudes also indicate the relative importance of each feature compared to the others. Fig. 4 displays the median absolute coefficients across all cross-validation folds, bounded by the first and third quartiles. As expected, the effective width emerged as the most important independent variable. However, the other covariates also showed smaller but notable contributions to swollen joint classification.

This work demonstrates that a logistic regression model combining a joint thickness measure, the effective width, with auxiliary variables such as age, BMI, sex, and joint type can serve as an effective tool for detecting interphalangeal joint swelling. The results highlight the value of effective width as an indicator of joint swelling, validated using

Fig. 4. Magnitudes of logistic regression coefficients indicating the importance of independent variables in classifying swollen joints. For each coefficient, the median value across all cross-validation folds is shown, with error bars representing the first and third quartiles.

a real-world dataset of photographs taken under varying conditions. Although promising, the model currently demonstrates greater variability in performance than is desirable, likely due to the limited number of positive (swollen) cases. Further validation on larger datasets is needed. With more data, the model could also be enhanced by incorporating interactions among independent variables to improve classification performance. Moreover, the proposed model holds promise for monitoring joint swelling in PsA patients over time, although this within-subject evaluation would require longitudinal photographic data from the same individuals. In the absence of a benchmark dataset and an established baseline method for this problem, the present work provides an initial contribution to the field.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Assessing swelling of interphalangeal joints is a crucial aspect of PsA diagnosis and management. In this work, we introduce a novel modeling approach based on logistic regression to digitally evaluate joint swelling using smartphone photographs of the hand. The model relies primarily on the effective width, an estimate of joint thickness ob-

tained through a computer vision process. Validated on a real-world dataset from 85 patients with PsA, our model achieved promising performance, highlighting its potential as a valuable tool for enhancing PsA assessment and paving the way for impactful future research.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank all patients and subjects who voluntarily participated in the present study.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Geijer, G.-M. Alenius, L. André, T. Husmark, P. T. Larsson, U. Lindqvist, I. Thyberg, and E. Theander, "Health-related quality of life in early psoriatic arthritis compared with early rheumatoid arthritis and a general population," in *Seminars in Arthritis and Rheumatism*, vol. 51, no. 1. Elsevier, 2021, pp. 246–252.
- [2] F. Alinaghi, M. Calov, L. E. Kristensen, D. D. Gladman, L. C. Coates, D. Jullien, A. B. Gottlieb, P. Gisondi, J. J. Wu, J. P. Thyssen *et al.*, "Prevalence of psoriatic arthritis in patients with psoriasis: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational and clinical studies," *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, vol. 80, no. 1, pp. 251–265, 2019.
- [3] A.-M. Liphardt, E. Manger, S. Liehr, L. Bieniek, A. Kleyer, D. Simon, K. Tascilar, M. Sticherling, J. Rech, G. Schett *et al.*, "Similar impact of psoriatic arthritis and rheumatoid arthritis on objective and subjective parameters of hand function," *ACR open rheumatology*, vol. 2, no. 12, pp. 734–740, 2020.
- [4] E. Dures, C. Bowen, M. Brooke, J. Lord, W. Tillet, N. McHugh, and S. Hewlett, "Diagnosis and initial management in psoriatic arthritis: a qualitative study with patients," *Rheumatology advances in practice*, vol. 3, no. 2, p. rkz022, 2019.
- [5] A. Ogdie, L. C. Coates, and P. Mease, "Measuring outcomes in psoriatic arthritis," *Arthritis care & research*, vol. 72, pp. 82–109, 2020.
- [6] J. Knitza, L. Gupta, and T. Hügler, "Rheumatology in the digital health era: status quo and quo vadis?" *Nature Reviews Rheumatology*, pp. 1–13, 2024.
- [7] D. E. Webster, R. H. Haberman, L. M. Perez-Chada, M. Tummacherla, A. Tediario, V. Yadav, E. C. Neto, W. MacDuffie, M. DePhillips, E. Sieg *et al.*, "Clinical validation of digitally acquired clinical data and machine learning models for remote measurement of psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis: a proof-of-concept study," *The Journal of Rheumatology*, vol. 51, no. 8, pp. 781–789, 2024.
- [8] C. Lugaresi, J. Tang, H. Nash, C. McClanahan, E. Uboweja, M. Hays, F. Zhang, C.-L. Chang, M. G. Yong, J. Lee *et al.*, "Mediapipe: A framework for building perception pipelines," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.08172*, 2019.
- [9] T. Hügler, L. Caratsch, M. Caorsi, J. Maglione, D. Dan, A. Dumusc, M. Blanchard, G. Kalweit, and M. Kalweit, "Dorsal finger fold recognition by convolutional neural networks for the detection and monitoring of joint swelling in patients with rheumatoid arthritis," *Digital Biomarkers*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 31–35, 2022.
- [10] S. Phatak, S. Chakraborty, and P. Goel, "Computer vision detects inflammatory arthritis in standardized smartphone photographs in an indian patient cohort," *Frontiers in Medicine*, vol. 10, p. 1280462, 2023.
- [11] L. J. Hadjileontiadis, V. Charisis, S. Hadjimiditriou, S. B. Dias, G. Apostolidis, G. Dimaridis, I. Kitsas, A. Karlas, N.-A. Fasoula, F. Levi-Schaffer *et al.*, "European advances in digital rheumatology: explainable insights and personalized digital health tools for psoriatic arthritis," *EClinicalMedicine*, vol. 84, 2025.
- [12] X. Qin, Z. Zhang, C. Huang, M. Dehghan, O. R. Zaiane, and M. Jagersand, "U2-net: Going deeper with nested u-structure for salient object detection," *Pattern recognition*, vol. 106, p. 107404, 2020.